

THE PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATING MEDICAL TERMS IN "BABURNAME" INTO RUSSIAN

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Abstract: The article analyzes the translation of medical terms based on the material of comparing the original and the translation of «Baburname» into Russian. The author considers the result of incorrect translation of terms from the point of view of the impact on the reader.

Keywords: terms, special vocabulary, translation techniques, Russian language, translation correspondence.

Аннотация: Мақолада "Бобурнома"нинг асли ва русча таржима матнини қиёслаш натижасида тиббиёт терминларининг ўгирилиши таҳлил қилинади. Муаллиф терминларнинг нотўғри таржимасини ўқувчига таъсири нуқтаи назаридан кўриб чиққан.

Калит сўзлар: терминлар, махсус лексика, таржима усуллари, рус тили, таржима мувофиқлиги.

Аннотация: В статье анализируется перевод медицинских терминов на материале сопоставления оригинала и перевода «Бабурнаме» на русский язык. Автор рассматривает результат неправильного перевода терминов с точки зрения воздействия на читателя.

Ключевые слова: термины, специальная лексика, приемы перевода, русский язык, переводческое соответствие.

Translation is identical or equivalent if the reaction of the foreign-speaking reader in all essential features corresponds to the reaction of the reader of the text in the source language. In the text of Baburname, the role of medical terminology is significant as a unique means of recreating the national and linguistic picture of the world of an individual people. The use of vocabulary related to the field of medicine in the original language in the text enhances the uniqueness of the famous work. Let's explain what is said in the book with specific examples.

«Ҳавоси бисёр мутааффиндур, кузлар безгак кўп бўлур» [5,с.36]/ "There is putrefaction in the air of Andijan, many people suffer from fever in autumn" [4, p.20]; «Баъзи жарохатқа марҳамдек дору қўяр эди» [5,с.94]/ "He applied medicine like ointment to some wounds" [4, p.92].

The translation of the text is carried out in two stages, which consists of an analysis of the original text with a deep understanding of the writer's linguistic picture and synthesis, i.e. in transferring the content into another language. In the translation process, both of these stages are closely related to each other. Understanding a text from the position of a translator makes it obligatory to make a final conclusion about the content of the translated text and to fully understand the source text and understand the foreign language text through the prism of the specific features of the Russian language. Currently, research is being conducted to

study the highly specialized vocabulary of translations, on ways to transfer the realities and terms of medicine in translated works into another language and the interpretation of difficult-to-translate terms through explanation of their semantics, as well as by identifying the advantages and difficulties of direct and indirect translation of the original works, etc.

The purpose of our article is to identify medical terms in the work "Baburname" by Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur and to classify thematic resources.

On the scale of Uzbek and foreign terminology in the historical and literary direction based on the works of Leychik V.M., Grinev S.V., Melnikov G.P., Superanskaya A.V., Podolskaya N.V., Vasilyeva N.V., Tatarinov V.A., A.Madvalieva, M.Umarkhodzhaev, Dadabaeva H., Abdushukurova B., Bektemirova H., Danilenko V.P., Ismoilova M., Sharapova A., Kholmanova Z., Khozhieva A., Begmatova E., etc. And scientists Usmankhadzhaev A., Abilov U., Turakhanova M., Kasimov A. carried out research based on the study of medical terminology. They considered medical terminology in grammatical and lexical-semantic terms. Researcher M. Navruzova devoted her work to the origin and formation of medical terms.

Despite the works of native and foreign scientists on medical terminology, in their particular use in literature, the study of the terminological vocabulary of the work still needs extensive research.

Babur's encyclopedic knowledge is manifested in Baburname in the use and description of scientific and special vocabulary, in particular, the explanation of medical concepts. In Baburname, the terms denoting concepts related to medicine were grouped into thematic groups as follows: medical professions, diseases, medicines and medical instruments.

The use of medical terms contributes to the enrichment of the language of artistic works with professional words that create an artistic picture of the world of the author of the work. The medical vocabulary of the analyzed work combines special and non-special medical names that function in scientific and other subsystems of the language. The main part of the medical vocabulary is medical terminology.

Medical terms are included in the verbal and semantic level of the writer's linguistic personality, which consists in the selection of terms, in the lexical content of thematic groups and in the methods of semantic transformation of terms. At the linguistic and cognitive level, terms are a means of revealing the writer's ideological intent. All these determine the special place of the term in creating an artistic picture of the writer's world.

Within the framework of this study, the term translation adequacy is interpreted in accordance with the relative equality of the reconstruction of the semantic modality of the source text, based on the uniqueness of any text and, consequently, the fundamental impossibility of selecting an exact match between the source and translated texts, as a relative equivalent reconstruction of the semantic modality of the original.

Not all terms meet this requirement even within the same category of terms, in our case, in the translation of a medical terms, for example: «Мафосил захмати жиҳатидин намоз қила олмас эди, рўза ҳам тутмас эди» [5, с. 128]/ [5, p. 128]/ "Due to disease of the joints [Sultan Hussein] could not pray, he also did not keep the fasting" [4, p.99]; «Яна бир бу ким, ул фурсатта андоқ от ўлати бўлдуким, тавила-тавила отлар йиқилиб ўла киришти» [5, p.43]/ "What is more, at that time, such a pestilence attacked the horses that they fell and died in whole shoals" [4, p.30]. This circumstance presents a certain difficulty for an accurate understanding of the text and complicates the work of the translator.

To convey the names of professions in medicine reflected in the essay of the epoch, the translator successfully used synonyms of the word. For example, "бахши" means "doctor, healer": "«мусоҳиб йўсунлуқ табиби»" [5, p.258] / "as a doctor" [4, p.215]. The activity of the doctor, bakhshi is based on the treatment of the patient with medicinal herbs, plants, their roots, infusion of flowers, fruits, etc. In the work, the term "healer" is also used for doctors. Healers, bakhshis are recognized as healers of all diseases and mental ailments. To denote "a doctor treating a person", there is also a double use of both terms: bakhshi, healer (doctor).

Let's compare: " Табиблар бу балога не чора қилғойлар " [5,p.133] / "How can healers help in this trouble?" [4,p.103]. The parallel use of the words tabib, bakhshi / healer, doctor and bakhshi; oriza, maraz, zam/ disease, ailment also confirms that these words are absolute synonyms. If the term healer is based on the object of treatment, then the basis of the bakhshi lexeme is human activity aimed at treatment. Bakhshi is also used in modern Uzbek. Two meanings of this word are marked in the explanatory dictionary. Bakhshi is used in dialects today mainly in the second meaning, which is recorded in the explanatory dictionary. He expresses "a healer who treats with universal methods and practices." The word is also used colloquially and means "treatment, healing".

In addition to the fact that the word tabib / healer, doctor, which took its place in the lexicon of the work is used in the meaning of "doctor", it should also be noted that the Arabic loan entered into a syntagmatic connection with a purely Turkic lexeme and participated in the development of the system of medical terms of that time «...менинг онам Қутлуқ Нигорхонимга хасба марази ориз бўлди, фасод қилдилар, ноқис воқиъ бўлди» [5, p.124] / My mother Kutluk Nigar khanum had a hasbe disease [4,p.126]; «Гандамакка тушганда, манга тунд резандалиқ бўлди» [5, p.185] / "... when we camped in Gandamak, I got a severe runny nose" [4,p.150].

Babur uses in his text terms denoting medical professions, names of various types of diseases, names of medicines and medical instruments «Шанба куни бир аёқ сут ичтим. Якшанба куни ҳам бир аёқ сут ичтим, «гили махтум» ни ҳам араққа ҳал қилиб ичдим» [5,p.218] / "On Saturday I drank a cup of milk, on Monday I also drank a cup of milk and drank more diluted printed clay" [4,p.251]; Менинг бутумнинг ярасига бучқоқ ёкмокни буюрди, фатила қўймади. Илдиздек нимани ҳам бир қатла едурди [5, p.94] / He ordered burnt wool to be applied to the wound on my thigh, but did not put a wick. In addition, he once gave me some kind of rootlet to eat [5, p.128].

It can be said that the presence of medical terms used in Baburname testifies to the author's deep knowledge in the field of medicine.

The use of medical vocabulary in the composition determines their cognitive value, and also allows for a deep understanding of the text. The presence of a large number of medical terms in Babur's memoirs required a careful search for translation correspondences of this vocabulary in Russian. The analysis of translation errors in Baburname showed that a professional translator should not only know the grammar and vocabulary of a foreign language, but also fully master the special vocabulary used in the original text, master the art of hermeneutics.

The typology of medical terms updated in Baburname, namely:

1) denoting a profession: bakhshi, surgeon, doctor / bakhshi, healer, physician, bonesetter.

2) diagnosis, diseases: bezgak, washat (plague), isitma, zocho kashi, Orza, oriza, delivery, count, Yara, buhkok, hasba, corruption, sabb kueng, mafosil, labor, pain, rodo, maraz, scoop, peak, kurgarg, dobgul, temperature, dehydration, ulitr, ulitr fever, tempera, fever, smallpox, measles, wound, Java, Chiri, bolognese, kulange, cold, expulsion from hunger seamless and hands, cough, paralysis, ear disease, malaise, rebellion, wing, food, etc.

3) denoting parts of the organism: shahrag, safro, leg, ildiz, et, burner, cone / bone, crown, hollow artery, vein, meat, foot, bile.

4) denoting medical instruments and ways of treatment: niche, treatment, fatila, yards, mushily / distraction, wick, treatment, clean crowe, needle piercing (dissected pus).

The study of the medical terminology of Baburname can shed light on the formation and development of this part of the terminology of the modern literary language, clarify some ideological and artistic issues of the work, because medical vocabulary is one of the most important parts of the structure of the work.

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